

BLOOD PLASMA L-ASCORBIC ACID CONCENTRATION FOR ORAL L-ASCORBIC ACID DOSAGE UP TO 12 GRAMS PER DAY

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Paper received: 30th October, 1973

For reprints please quote:
(73-12) 10-19-9

Three independent lines of reasoning have led to the suggestion (1) that 1 to 10 grams of L-ascorbic acid per day is the oral dosage range consistent with optimum health for most people. One of these lines of reasoning is based on evolution (2), one on L-ascorbic acid synthesis by animals (3), and one on common cold therapy experiments (1). It would be expected that an increase in oral L-ascorbic acid dosage would result in increased blood plasma concentrations of L-ascorbic and dehydroascorbic acids. We have measured these increased blood plasma concentrations in two young male subjects.

completed for subject 2 after day 9. The heavy solid line is a least-squares straight line fitted to the circled values.

There is a regular increase in plasma L-ascorbic and dehydroascorbic acids with increased oral dosages in the 1 to 10 gram per day range. The plasma level is approximately doubled by a 10-fold increase in oral dosage. The size of this increase is probably diminished by a concomitant increase in the metabolic utilization of L-ascorbic and dehydroascorbic acids. The initial rises in plasma levels on days 1 and 4 to values above the equilibration levels on the same dosages are also suggestive of increased metabolic utilization.

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Contribution No. 1 from the Institute of Orthomolecular Medicine, Menlo Park, California, U.S.A.

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Subject 1 was 21 years of age and had been receiving no vitamin supplement to his diet, Subject 2 was 23 years of age and had been receiving a multivitamin pill daily which was terminated one week before the beginning of the experiment. Dosages of 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, and 0.5 grams per hour were given to achieve daily dosages of 2.4, 4.8, 7.2, 9.6, and 12.0 grams per day respectively. During the first night, no L-ascorbic acid was given. Thereafter, the dose for the entire 8-hour sleep period was given immediately before sleep. Blood was drawn at 3.00 p.m. each day and the plasma was separated and assayed (4, 5) for L-ascorbic and dehydroascorbic acids. Figure 1 shows the results of these assays. The solid line is for subject 1 and the broken line is for subject 2. The upper curves are for the sum of L-ascorbic and dehydroascorbic acids and the lower curves are for dehydroascorbic acid alone.

The hourly dosages were arranged to allow maximum equilibration at 2.4, 4.8, 7.2 and 9.6 grams per day dosage within the 12-day experimental period. The circled values in figure 1 are the average plasma levels for the two subjects on the last days of these equilibration periods. The single value for subject 1 is used for day 12, since the experiment was not

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Cystic fibrosis is one of those diseases of development about which we know very little: it is known to be linked to inherited metabolic defects, it is a generalized disease thought to involve the pancreas, and it can be detected at birth or it may not develop until several years later. Cystic fibrosis is characterized by a voracious appetite without a concomitant gain in weight, and a persistent cough that fails to clear mucus from the respiratory tract, which may then give rise to secondary infection. On page 11 this month, Cohen & Daniel at the University of Illinois report on their studies of sera from patients who are homozygous and heterozygous for the cystic fibrosis gene. Using agglutination time in the presence of a flagellar bacterium *Proteus vulgaris*, a sensitive assay technique has been developed which can separate normals from carriers and can measure the progress of the disease in cystic fibrosis patients. It is shown that mild forms of the disease in adult carriers can appear in the forms of emphysema, peptic ulcer, bronchiectasis or chronic bronchitis.

A most interesting observation, which may be relevant to the cause of the disease and which could shed light on the problem of developmental diseases in general is described by Cohen & Daniel on page 12. Methylation of RNA in cultured leukocytes and fibroblasts occurs at a much slower rate in patients having cystic fibrosis than in their relatives, which in turn is less than in controls. Whether the biochemical lesion is an intrinsic defect in RNA synthesis, or is a result of decreased membrane permeability to RNA remains to be decided. However these points do raise several possibilities on the cause of developmental diseases, which may have several basic factors in common.

Several developmental diseases are genetic rather than environmental, although they may become active from a previously dormant condition as a result of a changing environment. This means that the biochemical lesions producing these diseases must lie either in the transcription of the DNA template into RNA, or in the translation of RNA into protein sequences by which the characters of the cell are expressed in relation to signals coming across the plasma membrane from neighbouring cells. A more recent approach has been that DNA can modulate signals, which are recognized by protein molecules acting as regulators of metabolism. There is a very detailed control of forces from the external environment, and inter-cellular communication from other cells in the tissue in terms of energy resulting from metabolism, and this is channelled into cellular growth, reproduction and differentiation. It has been suggested that the best candidate for a language of regulation of the cell plasma membrane is the enzyme adenyl cyclase. It occupies a central position in many diverse metabolic pathways, is very closely related to utilization of energy from ATP, and it is believed that there are continuous membrane connections from the invaginations of the plasma membrane (endoplasmic reticulum) to the nucleus. Adenyl cyclase is present in greatest specific activity in nerve tissue, and consequently diseases of development — *i.e.* those which affect growing or differentiating tissue — tend to comprise many neurological diseases. Perhaps the Duchenne muscular dystrophy is the best example of a sex-linked disease of development, where skeletal muscle develops normally at first, but is followed by progressive wasting away of the muscle: the protein myofilaments are replaced by fat, and the biochemical lesion here is thought to occur at the site of excitation-contraction coupling,

International Research Communications System/**Medical Science**

IRCS

Journal

of International
Research
Communications

December 1973

Volume 1 no. 10